

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC SCIENCE IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT: The art of music has a direct and strong influence on a person from his youth holds a great place in its general cultural development. A democratic society is cultural music plays a bigger role in a person's life throughout his life is a constant companion. Music is the only art that is very deep in the human heart penetrated and acquired the power to vividly express this heart. So, it is true that music has a proper place in raising a generation worthy of our ancestors the truth is that it is up to us to do the honorable work of aesthetic education of a child, i.e. lays great responsibility on future personnel.

KEY WORDS: Music, ancestor, generation, upbringing, aesthetic, tradition, art, creative, society, child, soul, spiritual

The importance and tasks of musical literacy in primary education classes and in the family All the educational work carried out will instill these noble qualities in the young generation depends on formation from age. In fact, learning music literacy is kindergarten starts from age. Many children attend kindergarten during preschool education. they develop basic musical skills in kindergarten music classes. Learned many songs and games along with rhythm and dance moves they will meet. Children raised at home also have a certain musical imagination will be: a number of musical works broadcast on radio and television will be familiar. Although this knowledge is not systematized, music is teacher to that knowledge in forming theoretical concepts of music in children can lean to a certain extent. For music education in children's institutions the foundation is laid, therefore, the music director should be especially familiar with the teaching methodology, age and individual characteristics of small children of kindergarten age, their music and it is necessary to have a deep knowledge of the possibilities of singing. Conditionally two music education can be divided into stages. The first is the preparation stage. This is the main thing the goal is to develop children's musical skills. During this time, children learn to distinguish specific features of musical sounds, such as pitch and pitch and should learn and prepare to learn musical notation. Note in the second stage letter, i.e. direct representation of musical sounds in a graphic way - sheet music begins to study. In the course of music lessons, the child makes musical images of real life perceives through. Children's age-appropriate musical works are unforgettable in children makes an impression, enriches their spiritual world.

Musical education in school conditions is carried out in an integral connection with fiction and visual arts.

The method of chanting, listening to musical works of the genre, in particular instrumental pieces with a plot, music training in the process of playing musical games and dancing it is often defined by an artistic word. The child vividly imagines artistic images and works of fine art are effectively used for deep understanding. Every music lesson conducted using methods is artistic for children awakens aesthetic pleasure, develops their feelings, creative thinking and speech grows. In addition, musical games and dances rhythm in children develops the skills of feeling, agility and mobility, and correct stature helps to grow.

Music is aesthetic education, on the way to harmonious education of a person of a democratic society it should become a component of the ongoing work. Musical with children work is especially important. Music is a strong emotion in a child's heart evokes feelings. So, the art of music and education are human qualities in a person developing the inner world of a person, which calls for spiritual purification and elevation powerful that enriches, strengthens faith, will, and awakens creativity inner strength - ensures the rise of spirituality. His art with the help of music his perception grows and his feelings become richer. Without developing musical perception in children, comprehensively, without sufficiently indulging their love of music; it is impossible to educate rich physical, spiritual and strict moral qualities. According to Plato , Greek philosopher, the power of the state depends on what kind of music, what tone and what it directly depends on the fact that it sounds in rhythm.

Music from a young age awakened interest affects the strength of a person's further musical development, and it provides the formation of skills and tastes, educates a good musical taste. Music is a great source of aesthetic and spiritual mood. Children's feelings of music and taking into account its great influence on the formation, understanding and feeling of its content appropriate use of a musical work that correctly reflects truth and reality has a special place. The main source of formation of musical images is nature and people it directly depends on his speech and perception of beauty in the surrounding world. Ibn Sino also recognized the power of emotional influence of music and made it his medicine recommended as a healing program in the treatment of mental illnesses. In one place in the work "The Law of Medicine", he assessed the spiritual influence of music. He defined the importance of infant in education as follows: "The body of a child is trained two things are necessary for him: one is

to rock him slowly, and the other is his mother's song (God). The first belongs to the body, the second to the soul." Children of preschool age to see the bright future of our country in the form of music education and its development it will be possible. For this, it is necessary to have well-thought-out, specific goals and tasks promising programs have been developed. Musical perception It is important to define the function and content. These are all-round development of the individual, among others, aesthetic education is related to tasks and determined by common goals. Such tasks are to attract children to activities in the field of music, artistic music development of aesthetic perception and emotional mastery, love for it education, development of musical ability, formation of musical taste, artistic in children should be to develop creative talent.

The great influence of music on the child's feelings and aspirations, content and feeling taking into account, it is appropriate from a musical work that accurately reflects reality use has a special place. Human thinking and expression for musical art feelings serve as the basis. Music is the beginning of speech in the development of harmony with sound and dance-related food. The music matches the rhythm of the labor movement it makes it easier to unite people who are striving for a goal. Speech as a result of generalization of tones, rhythms of labor processes and musical tones folk music is formed. Music based on folk art sources is always attractive and evokes different emotions in the heart. At the same time, in music to sounds and there are cases of imitation of figurative situations, but the essence of the matter is with them not specified. A musical image is related to its clear appearance.

The future of independent Uzbekistan, the development of tomorrow, is the future it is important to raise children as aesthetically and spiritually rich, educated individuals. This music has a special place and its own characteristics in the realization of the goal. Musical education in pre-school educational institutions is a clear goal directed, for instance, the aesthetic, moral, intellectual development of the preschool child increase, educate the child as a person, expand his worldview, his talent to be able to express, understand music aesthetically, approach it creatively is to teach to receive. Each child learns which direction of music regardless of his age characteristics, psychological development is meant by the music director necessary.

All in all, it is the defining beginning of the entire educational process that continues continuously type is called "primary education". This is the only approach to education it is enough to look at it with kindness and justice.

Because today's young generations are in the 21st century to the active members of our society, full of strength, healthy, educated and intelligent. The great task of converting lies with the music leader and teacher. If the courage, strength, knowledge of our young people and; If we can combine patriotism with the help of music, we will find more power we can't.

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